

Aesthetics and Socio-Cultural Functions of Two Hindi Satirical Fake News Columns: *Sattū jī kī asatya kathāem* and *Pappū aur Gappū kī baiṭh'kī*

Fabio Mangravit

Abstract

The article is a first attempt to investigate the field of the satirical fake news in Hindi. To study this subject, the text focuses on the columns *Sattū jī kī asatya kathāem* (“Sattu ji’s Fake News”) and *Pappū aur Gappū kī baiṭh'kī* (“Pappū aur Gappū’ meeting”), authored by the noted columnist and satirist Ajay Shukla (Ajay Śukla). Both of them were published during the Coronavirus pandemic, on *Jan'sattā*, a well-known daily journal in Hindi. The article, after a broader analysis of the main features of the satirical fake news, engages in a study of the aesthetics and socio-cultural functions epitomized by these texts in India during the pandemic. As far as the aesthetical side of the columns is considered, the article considers the relationship between the field of satirical fake news and proper fake news. The analysis explores the socio-cultural functions embodied by these columns emphasizes their role, during the pandemic, in the fulfilment of a variety of functions.

Keywords: Hindi literature, fake news, satire, Coronavirus, new media.

1. Introducing the Socio-cultural Functions of Satirical Fake News¹

Quite common is the perspective in which satire, intended as a mode which performs a “communicative” function, has played, especially over the last years, a “therapeutic” and “informative” role in addressing a variety of socio-cultural and political problems which have affected different communities on a global level. Satire is an instrument that we

1 This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the call under the Call HORIZON-MSCA-2023-PF-01. Project 101152854. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

can embrace to re-adapt the self to individual and collective trauma (Declercq 2021: 2-3); at the same time, it has also been used in many contexts and in a transdisciplinary way as a trigger to raise criticism and to enhance awareness about a variety of problems. "Satirical activism", writes Yu, author of a recent study of the uses of humour and satire in China during and after the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic in the country, uses "satire, humor, or humorous formats and genres to voice dissent and evoke collective resistance to dominant discourse" (Yu 2024). Alongside the rise of satire as a means to raise criticisms and evoke resistance by global counter-publics, the last five years have witnessed the emergence and/or the re-enforcement of a variety of new digital forms of doing satire. Memes are important instruments of political contestation, and are being used by global minorities to voice their socio-cultural claims and re-imagine a more democratic and inclusive future. For sure, the spread of the "memes culture" has been also criticized for promoting "a rapid trade in attention grabbing ideas, over slower-burning systematic, contextualized thinking" (Owens 2019: 106). This culture has revealed its relevance also in the Global South, where, as recently demonstrated by a variety of studies, memes have been used in many cases by subaltern and marginalized groups to embody new forms of resistance (Jain & Shivaprasad 2022: 153-178). Alongside the spread of the meme culture on the new media, an often-underestimated effect of this dynamics regards the impact of digitalization on a variety of other cultural areas connected to the modes of humour and satire. In a variety of global contexts, for example, the need to contain the spread of the Coronavirus has led performative arts to deeply modify their methods of transmission and reception.

Among the fields which establish a connection to the area of journalism and/or literature and which have received new impulses during the pandemic, we should also remember the field of the so-called "satirical fake news", a category of texts which has recently been at the center of a vibrant juridical and psycho-linguistic debate (Golbeck et al. 2018: 17-21; Horne & Adali 2017: 759– 766; Low et al. 2022). Satirical fake news is essentially texts that emulate proper journalistic sources with a humorous and/or satirical aim. In this sense, they are texts that are employed by their authors with the intent of expressing ideas, often with a parodic and grotesque dimension, to produce counter-narratives and/or to criticize a certain socio-cultural or political aspect of the society. Remarkably, the field of the satirical fake news has existed in many global contexts well before the processes of digitalization which have been so-far explained. Indeed, the field of satire and, more

particularly, that of literary satire, have always been characterized by the tendency to emulate, often in a magmatic and “parasitic” (Harder 2012: 167) way, other literary and extra-literary genres. The relationship established by satire with the field journalism is extremely old. Some of the authors who, at least in the history of European literatures, have contributed to the development of satire as a distinct literary sphere in the 18th century have, for example, emulated and distorted in a grotesque way the moralist orientation of pamphlets (Hedrick 2017). Similarly, a variety of texts with a clear-cut parodic and satirical function have emulated, in a “mediatic” way,² texts usually associated with journalism. This is, for example, the case of the fictionalized /imaginary interviews that appeared in different formats and in different global contexts, especially from the 1950s to the mid-1970s (Gallerani 2022).

2. Fake News and Satirical Fake News: Analogies and Differentiations

It must be highlighted that the idea of publishing journals characterized by a specific satirical value and characterized by a façade of “factuality” is also not a recent cultural phenomenon. In the first half of the 18th century one of the earliest authors to engage in the writing of this kind of texts was Jonathan Swift, followed in the 19th century by Mark Twain. In the course of the 20th century, and particularly in the 1970s, a variety of journals were conceived by their authors with the objective of emulating the factuality of a proper journal. The texts usually had a double function: on the one side, they were often used by their authors as instruments to raise socio-cultural and political awareness and produce a “counter-public” during historical periods in which the use of such texts was instrumental to creating ideological and political opposition. At the same time, however, this type of journals also granted the opportunity to well-known writers to pursue new literary and aesthetical experiments. In French a famous satirical journal that was published with the objective of emulating proper news was *Le Canard enchaîné*, published since 1915 and authored by Maurice Maréchal.³

2 The term “mediatic” was recently adopted to describe this kind of texts by Gallerani (2022), author of a diachronic study on the history of “imaginary interviews” (*intervista immaginata* in Italian) in various European literatures in the 1960s and 1970s. Gallerani noted that these texts, often characterised by a clear-cut use of humour and satire, originally emerged as a development of the proper interviews and had originally had a “paratextual value”.

3 Cfr. Cariguel (2017); Martin (2000a); Martin (2003).

Similarly, in Italy the journal *Il Male*,⁴ emulating more famous daily journals, hosted texts by internationally known authors such as Umberto Eco, Leonardo Sciascia and Italo Calvino.⁵

The novelty regarding the satirical journals and fake news which appeared in the course of the last ten years is that fake news has become a quite common and dramatical issue that, especially during the Coronavirus pandemic, negatively affected the public by spreading misleading and confusing ideas about the virus. Obviously, the socio-cultural, political and ideological value of fake news has many repercussions and is currently impacting different aspects of contemporary society. In this theoretical context, also the aesthetical and juridical dimension of the satirical fake news has changed. Indeed, as a variety of previous studies reveal, with the spread of the new media and the digitalization of satire, it seems sometimes hard to make a clear-cut distinction between satirical and proper fake news.⁶ “If one accepts our premise that satire should be considered as distinct from fake news, the question now turns to finding the criteria that will allow us to label articles as either satire or fake news” (Low et al. 2022). To answer this crucial question, a possible theoretical distinction between these two categories could regard the alleged absence of factuality in the field of the fake news; indeed, while fake news usually does not narrate a fact, the satirical news, by contrast, often – but not always – conveys an inner “truth” which, despite not being represented by the narrated facts, stays at the center of the parrhesian strategies pursued by the satirist (ibid.). Satires, especially those inspired by an observational dimension, often attempt to produce a reflection on reality. In this sense, as claimed in the past, satire could also be associated with philosophy (Diehl 2013: 311-321). Another possible interpretation of the difference between these areas could lie in the different intent which is pursued by the authors of these texts; indeed, while “news articles [...] are intentionally and verifiably false, and could mislead readers”, the satirical news is “factually incorrect, but

4 The journal “*Il Male*” was founded by Pino Zac in 1978 and kept playing a crucial socio-cultural and ideological role in Italy till 1982, when it ceased to be published. Remarkably, this Italian journal emulated in a grotesque and satirical way famous Italian daily journals, such as “*L’Unita*”, and “*La Repubblica*”.

5 In 1979 Italo Calvino decided to publish on this journal a preview of one chapter of the book *Se una notte d’inverno un viaggiatore*. Cfr. <https://ilmanifesto.it/quando-calvino-scrisse-sul-male-poi-venne-limmobilismo-molisano>.

6 This difficulty in making a distinction between these areas has been clarified, for example, by the recent experiments made with the AI to establish a psycholinguistic difference between these areas. Indeed, “fake news bears a lot of textual cues that make it resemble satirical news more than real news” (Low et al. 2022).

the intent is not to deceive but rather to call out, ridicule, or expose behaviour that is shameful, corrupt, or otherwise 'bad'" (Golbeck et al. 2018).

As for the juridical dimension of these fields, it is not easy to establish which are the limits and responsibilities of satire. Indeed, even though one of the principles on which democracies are based is the freedom of speech,⁷ it must be considered that satirists, not less than any other citizen, are also subject to a variety of juridical limits. In many global contexts satirical texts can be connected to crimes such as slander and contempt (Boggero 2020: 6). Moreover, apart from these juridical limitations, satirists must always face, in any given socio-cultural and political context, a variety of other types of pressure which can lead the authors to adopt forms of self-censorship, even if there is not any explicit official censorship. This issue, if we consider the uses of censorship in the South Asian context, has been at the center of heated debates, especially when satirists have authored jokes concerning politics and religion. There are famous cases in point in stand-up comedy.⁸ In the comparison between fake news and satirical texts, another problem concerns the "uptake"⁹ of satirical jokes by the audience. Indeed, if one of the main features of the satirical news is that of creating a feeling of estrangement in the reader, it should at the same time and by virtue of this mechanism allow the readers to grasp the fictitious nature of the narrated news. The ability on the part of the readers to understand the fictional character of the news also depends on the previous knowledge and ability to distinguish fake news from satirical news.

7 In Europe, this is regulated by Article 11 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (CFREU) and by Article 10 of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), which recognise and protect freedom of opinion (Boggero 2020: 5).

8 In India, stand-up comedians such as and Aditi Mittal, Sanjay Rajoura have lamented the presence of a variety of juridical limits to expression; quite famous is, for example, the case of the comic Munawar Faruqui, who was arrested on 2 January 2021 with the charge of having authored jokes which offended Hindu faith. An article on these themes, titled "No Country for Political Satire: How Much Can Indian Comedy Really Push the Boundaries?", has been recently published on "DeadAnt". It is available at:<<https://deadant.co/no-country-for-political-satire>>.

9 The notion of uptake is used here primarily by referring the theorization of Simpson, who authored in 2000 a discourse analysis model of satire named SMUT, an acronym comprising four elements, "setting", "method", "uptake" and "target". The uptake of satire refers to the ability by the audience to understand the satirical content of the joke. Cfr. Simpson (2000).

Given the difficulty to trace a clear-cut distinction between these areas, we could postulate, on the basis of some previous theoretical reflections on the nature of satirical fake news, that the latter is *generally*, but *not necessarily*, characterized by a few aesthetical elements that allow the reader to recognize them. It is one of the most common aesthetical characteristics of satirical fake news that they, in emulation of proper news, generally show an insistent use of nominal phrases. Moreover, the satirical news is often characterized by the presence of a climax, which is achieved through the juxtaposition of adjectives that put emphasis on a specific moral aspect of the satirized subjects. It must be noted that satirical fake news generally employs an archaic phraseology and/or adopts sound bites (Palermo 2016: 426-427).

Finally, it could be also added to these observations that, generally, satirical fake news reveals an emphatic character and have, in many cases, also an artistic and creative dimension. The creative dimension of the satirical fake news is, doubtless, hard to define; however, it is worth noting that satirical fake news, in contrast to proper news, display different layers of intertextuality. Such intertextuality could also imply the adoption of elements which are ostensibly fictitious. This, for example, could entail a reference to facts concerning religious, historical and mythical figures. It has been argued that one of the merits of satirical fake news is that of helping their audience – if they detect its fictive character – to train their critical thinking and distinguish between fictive and factual news (Low et al. 2022). This, for example, was one of the ideological objectives pursued by the Italian journal *Il Male* in the historical period in which it started being published (Palermo 2016).

In the 2000s, with the explosion of the fake news on the World Wide Web, such informative value of the satirical fake news apparently became even more important. Indeed, the fake news could embody, in a way which could be even more marked than in the past, an informative function in making the public conscious about the possibilities of misrepresentation which are inherent to the new media. In this way, the satirical character inherent to the satirical news could fully embody what Diehl calls the “philosophical” nature of satire. Nevertheless, even the ethical duties and responsibilities deriving from the production of satirical fake news are more ambiguous and harder to define. While in the past, the public of satirical news mainly consisted of buyers of satirical journals who thus were conscious of being ‘cheated’ by the authors’ texts, nowadays the ‘victims’ of these texts – especially when they are published in an online format – may miss the fictive character of the sources.

3. The Publication of Three Hindi Satirical Columns During the Pandemic

Sattū jī kī asatya kathāem and *Pappū aur Gappū kī baiḥh'kī* are two literary columns, published of the daily journal *Jan'sattā*, which have been authored in 2020 by the writer and satirist Ajay Shukla (Ajay Śukla). All of them have been published between 22 May, 2020 and 12 June, 2020. In this sense, they are interesting evidences of the use of humour and satire at a historic moment which was crucial for the spread of the Coronavirus in India. Moreover, they reveal the distinct and somehow specific way in which the 'genre' of the satirical news established itself in India in the last years. They were published on a specific web-page connected to the daily journal *Jan'sattā* which contains 'news' characterized by the presence of humour. Shukla is an author who was engaged in writing texts of satire (*vyāṅgya*) and humour (*hāsyā*) even before the spread of the pandemic. Among his previous works, it is worth mentioning the drama *Tāj'mahal kā teṇḍar*, a work in which Shukla, drawing inspiration from Indian history and particularly from the story or biography of the Moghul Emperor Shah Jahan, attempted to portray the inefficiency of Indian administration in contemporary times.¹⁰ Moreover, apart from this classic of contemporary Hindi satire, Shukla has written a variety of other sketches, short-stories and dramas with grotesque and satirical themes.

The idea of writing such satirical columns was not new. Indeed, since the 1950s and 1960s, a variety of satirical authors have been committed to writing texts where they, often adopting symbolisms and values from Indian past, could obliquely project their own reflection on Indian contemporary society (Mangraviti 2020). The representation of the "contradictions" of Indian society, as well noted by Kamaleshvar (Kam'leśvar), one of the main voices of the *Nayī kahānī* in the 1960s, is at the center of Indian satire (1966: 16). One of the most famous Hindi satirists to move in this direction was, for example, Harishankar Parsai (Hariśaṅkar Par'sāi), who authored satires often imbued in Indian *bhakti* ambiance. Remarkably, Parsai was also one of the earliest Hindi writers to venture into the field of the "imaginary interviews" (*kālp'nik sāksātkār*), texts which, not unlike the satirical fake news, tended to emulate the plain,

10 This drama narrates the administrative issues faced by the Moghul Emperor, if he were alive in contemporary Indian society, to build the Tāj Mahal. Over the last years, this satirical drama has been staged by many theatrical groups. Cfr. <<https://chitralkha.co.in/ramakanta-samantaray-on-taj-mahal-ki-tender-theatre/>>.

simple language of proper journalist texts. Hindi literary satirists have also reflected on the philosophical and cosmological value of *māyā*, a divine entity which is deeply connected to the notions of *thag'nā* ("cheating") and which, in Hindu religious tradition, is responsible for the 'fake' character of the mundane dimension. Interestingly, the reflection on *māyā* also epitomized an ideological and political value in Hindi literary satire. The history /ies of Indian literary satire, from this perspective, have often been permeated by an obsessive will to describe the false and fictitious nature of any all-encompassing metanarrative describing reality. Nevertheless, while the idea of using literary columns to talk about the problems of the present was not new as such, a quite interesting novelty characterizing Shukla's columns consisted in the will to write "fake" (*asatya*) news by drawing inspiration from the facts occurring in Indian society during the period of the pandemic.

4. Aesthetics and Main Leitmotifs of the Satirical Fake News

Interestingly, unlike other satirical news published in other global contexts before and during the pandemic, the texts authored by Shukla clearly revealed their fictive nature, since all of them were inserted in a specific and distinct page of the journal *Jan'sattā*. In addition, a variety of other aesthetical and paratextual elements could lead the audience to grasp the fictitious nature of the texts. First and foremost, it is worth noting that the web page containing all the texts is marked by the presence of the word *hyūmar* - the Devanagari transliteration of the word 'humour' - which immediately suggests to readers of *Jan'sattā* that this page contains only humorous texts. This is an important element because it shows that readers are self-conscious 'victims' who, before deciding to access the content of these columns, have been made aware by the magazine of the nature of the texts they are about to read. Another important paratextual element is given by the presence of two editorial cartoons. In each of these, the reader can see some common elements, such as a picture depicting the fictional characters/narrators of the columns and a photograph of the columnist. Next to the photograph of the columnist, the reader can see the word *vyaᅅgya*, suggesting the satirical nature of the texts.

The most important element which suggested this dimension regarded the presence, in the title of the single 'news' items, of terms such as "fake news" and "*asatya kathāem*", which right away revealed the fictitious nature of the texts.

Such reflections on the paratextual strategies are particularly significant in this context: indeed, not all texts that are usually encapsulated in the field of the satirical columns suggest and/or overtly indicate their fictitious nature. Remarkably, not all the satirical news which found place in the e-page of the journal *Jan'sattā* dedicated to satire and humour showed the presence of cartoons. These pictures, therefore, were deployed as a 'trademark' to signal the authorship of Ajay Shukla. Another element which differentiates these columns from other examples is the highly differentiated nature of the narrative registers used by Shukla in authoring these satirical sketches. A few texts were conceived more as short stories (*kahānī*) than as satirical news; indeed, they tend to have a slightly more articulate style than that found in other satirical fake news of the same author:

He was lying covered in sand on the banks of the north flowing Ganga in Sultanganj. His breathing, heartbeat, pulse - all were missing. His clothes were wet. Perhaps he had jumped into the water with his clothes due to the heat of the afternoon. Some migrant labourers bathing in the Ganga saw him. They ran towards him.¹¹

The majority of the other texts are characterized by the adoption of the following narrative scheme: the author, drawing inspiration from facts occurring in the Indian public sphere, creates hidden details and/or news (*khab'reṃ*) and curiosities about eminent political figures and topics. In these cases, the model deployed by Shukla in developing these narratives follows quite well the model we have envisaged in other global contexts. The language is plain and inspired by everyday language, the syntax based on a paratactic style, and the phraseology relying on sound bites.¹² A good example of the narrative structure that tends to emulate proper news can be found, for example, at the

11 vah Sul'tāngāñj meṃ uttār'vāhinī Gaṅgā ke taṭ par bālū meṃ sanā parā thā. Sāṃs, dhaṛ'kan, nabz-sab gāyab. kap'ṛe gile the. śāyad dopahr kī gar'mī se tarap kar vah kap'rom ke sāth pānī meṃ utar gayā thā.

Cfr. the satirical news available at: <<https://www.jansatta.com/humour/how-religious-discrimination-affecting-indias-culture-and-image-read-this-story/1435152/>>.

12 From this point of view, it is worth noting that the satirical fake news is generally inspired by the style of the tabloids, which, more than other magazines, tend to have a sensationalist and essentialist approach to the narration of facts. After all, as Rogers and Niederer have recently pointed out, tabloids, especially in the second half of the 19th century, contributed to the rise of fake news as a cultural phenomenon (2020: 51). The satirical fake news, from this perspective, by emulating in a satirical way this kind of journals, could have also subtly contributed to create a counter-narrative against this kind of news.

beginning of the *khobar Gañjā-bhāring kī bhī dukāneṃ khuleṃ, varnā das hazār naśebāz Kaśī Viśvanāth ke āge demge dhar'nā* ("Ganja and drug shops should open, otherwise ten thousand drug addicts will fast in front of Kaśī Viśvanāth").

New Delhi. The All India (Non-Alcoholic) Addicts Association has appealed to the Prime Minister that like the drunkards community, they should also be given an opportunity to contribute in the interest of the country. A delegation of the association went to the Prime Minister's residence on Thursday morning and submitted a memorandum.¹³

Some texts also assume the character of a 'report', of 'rumors' produced by Sattū or, in *Pappū aur Gappū kī baiṭh'kī*, by Pappū and Gappū, for investigating socio-cultural habits of Indian society. The presence of these figures is, from this perspective, an essential in all the texts authored by Shukla: the meetings between them and/or with other figures are often used as a pretext to stage the rumours that these characters express in the stories. Similar characters are also quite common in many of the Hindi satirical columns published during the second half of the 20th century.¹⁴ Remarkably, all the texts, in spite of their narrative differences, are characterized by the adoption of a title in Hindi and by a brief description in Hindi and/or in English, generally used by the author to comment the satirical content of the titles. If the narrative registers and techniques used by the author are quite differentiated, not less heterogeneous are the motifs treated by the author. The most frequently treated topic of the satirical fake news regarded the pandemic, particularly the measures taken by Indian administration to regulate and to prevent the spread of it in Indian territory. This topic was at the center of the satirical news *Covid-19 se bac'ne se rāṣṭrapati ne pār kiyā arab sāgar, nām badal hoṭal meṃ liyā kam'rā* ("The president, who escaped Covid-19, crossed the Arabian Sea, changed his name and took a hotel room"), *Koronā par kaibinet kī baṛī baiṭhak, JS ke sujhāv par bha'ke PS* ("Big Cabinet Meeting on Corona Issue: Senior Minister Flares up for Joint

13 nāi dillī. akhil bhār'tiy (gair-śarābī) naśebāz saṅgh ne pradhānmantrī se apil kī hai ki bev'rā samāj kī tarah un'ko bhī deśhit meṃ yog'dān kar'ne kā av'sar pradān kiyā jāe. saṅgh ke ek pratidinhi maṅḍal ne guruvār kī subah pradhānmantrī ke āvās par jā kar ek jñāpan sauṃpā.

Cfr. the satirical news available at: <<https://www.jansatta.com/humour/covid-19-ways-to-improve-the-economy-in-this-corona-crisis/1420840/>>.

14 The presence of ancillary characters who spread rumors is common, for example, in the columns of Harishankar Parsai and, more in particular, in the column "Kabirā kharā bāzār meṃ", issued in *Sārikā* in the mid-1970s.

Minister's Suggestion"), *Koronā ko bhag'vān kī ciṭṭī, paṛh'kar hil gāim sab'kī cūleṃ* ("By Reading God's Letter to Corona the Joints of All will Be Shaken").

Apart from these sketches, in which the political and socio-cultural situation during the pandemic is treated directly by the author, other themes tended to emerge in the texts. Some of them reveal a clear-cut connection to some of the most common motifs of Hindi literary satire. The classical moral motif concerning the consumption of drugs – which was treated by Indian satires since the 19th century – was, for example, at the center of the above-mentioned *Gaṅjā-bhāṅg kī bhī dukāneṃ khuleṃ*, where the author proposes to legalize drugs to "improve the economy in this Corona crisis". Another topic which connects the short stories and news produced by Shukla to the main topoi of Hindi literary satire regards the motif of the *baglā-bhagat*, the false devotee and/or hypocritical person involved in the political and religious spheres.¹⁵ This kind of literary topos can be found, for example, in the short story *Vyaṅgya: ek pyāse brāhmaṇ kī prem'kathā* ("Satire: The Love-Story of a Thirsty Brahman"). The narration of Brahmans who indulge in "thirsty" and licentious desires is also quite common in Hindi literature and traces a fil rouge that leads from Phanishvar'nāth Renu's (Phaniśvar'nāth Renu) *Mailā āṃcal* (1954) to Harishankar Parsai's (Hariśaṅkar Par'sāi's) short stories.

Here it is worth noting the adaptation of symbols and values from an Indian religious background. The reference to historical figures associated with this *paramparā* (tradition) can be found, for example, in *Vyaṅgya: svarg ke geṭ se lauṭāe gae jumman, Citragupt ne kahā: abhī dīn pūre nahīm hue*, whose main topic is to describe how religious discrimination affects India's culture and image. The tendency to adopt symbolism associated with Citragupta, the Hindu registrar of the dead people, is pivotal to the history of Hindi literary satire. Indeed, a similar characterization was often adopted by Hindi satirists to develop criticisms of Indian bureaucracy. It is remarkable, however, that such a reference to the notion of death is made in an historical period in which images of deaths caused by the Coronavirus were used in many Indian and global mass media. Two crucial political topics which were at the center of the debates in Indian public sphere during and after the end of the pandemic and which found space in these columns regarded the 2020–21 Indian farmers' protests and the internal and external migration flow from and to India during the pandemic. We have to register the presence in many *khab'reṃ* of ecological themes, often articulated by the author of

15 The author thanks one of the two anonymous reviewers for detecting the presence of this motif in the satirical columns.

the sketches by drawing inspiration from spiritual and mystical elements. Finally, it is worth noting that in parallel with the publication of Shukla's satirical fake news, other artistic attempts were made to narrate in a humorous and/or grotesque way aspects of Indian society during the pandemic, e.g. issues related to job loss, couple relationships during the lockdown, social ostracism of health workers, scepticism towards vaccination and the pharmaceutical industry, etc. However, such topics, which were at the centre of the production of other writers and artists, were not or were only marginally addressed through the use of satirical fake news by Shukla.¹⁶

5. Interrogating the present society by staging satirical fake news

In the light of the broader considerations on the uses embodied by satirical fake news in different global contexts and, more in particular, in Indian society during the Covid-19 pandemic, it is worth pondering on the socio-cultural functions expressed by the news and short stories authored by Ajay Shukla, and reflecting on the ethical and informative value of writing texts characterized by an aesthetical component of 'fakeness' during an historical period that was characterized by the spread of fake news. If, on the one hand, the satirical news can embody an informative value in training the audience to detect proper fake news, they could, on the other, also – not less than proper fake news – contribute to the dissemination of cultural bias. From this perspective, Shukla's texts, while sharing the characteristics of satirical news, never aimed at misleading the possible reader by producing news which would resemble and appear like real news. They are marked as satirical by virtue of the many elements which signal their overt fictional character. Their fictionality is always clearly manifested by the highly grotesque and emphatic character of the narrative style adopted by the author. Moreover, the presence of fictional characters who introduced the rumors also contributed to make these texts 'fancy' and different in many ways from the common fake news.

Nonetheless, it seems that Shukla's satirical news shared with other satirical texts produced before and during the pandemic, the specificity of embodying some, quite distinct specific socio-cultural objectives. Their main objective was to foster, even if mediated by a highly recognizable lens of fictionality, a critical thinking in the readers. It is

16 For a broader analysis on literary, performative and digital uses of humour and satire in Hindi during the pandemic, cfr. Mangraviti (2023).

known that, especially in 2021, Indian and other global public spheres were affected by the outburst of a variety of clichés, many of which related migrant workers.¹⁷ Other events which impacted and polarized the Indian public sphere were the above-mentioned farmers' protests of 2020-2021 and, with regard to the second wave of the Coronavirus in India, the impact on the spreading of the pandemic produced by the 2021 Kumbh Mela which, according to some Indian journals published during that age, "seeded Covid across India".¹⁸

The present study does not intend to take any political stance with regard to these debates. However, it is important to note at least two factors which are of crucial importance if considered in the broader analysis of the functions played by the Hindi satirical fake news under scrutiny. The first regards the role played by fake news, also through the agency of memes, in spreading socio-cultural misconceptions, especially in relation to marginalized categories and groups in India and in other global contexts during the pandemic. The second aspect relates to the fact that in India, not unlike what happened in many global contexts, some politicians also backed some of the narratives that, at a later stage of the pandemic, turned out to be fake news. In this general context, it is important to note that Shukla's satirical fake news generally revealed multilateral ways of creatively and satirically re-adapting some of the cultural clichés and stereotypes characterizing Indian public sphere during the pandemic. With regard to certain topics, the author presented critical counter-narratives with regard to the management of the pandemic:

New Delhi. After the graduation at the university, spiritual leaders [*ācārya*] will be appointed for higher education. The masters will stay

17 With regard to the representation of the labour migrants in Indian public sphere during the pandemic, it has been noted that the discrimination in India during the pandemic had different social dimensions. Objects of stigmatization in India were, for example, North-east Indians; also, the marginalization had a socio-cultural, political and religious value. As a general rule, the label 'migrant' "was reserved to refer people belonging to the lower sociocultural strata" and, as recently stated, suggested "how fear-ridden powerful systems victimize and blame the helpless marginalized groups" (Bhanot et al. 2021).

18 Cfr: <<https://www.theguardian.com/world/2021/may/30/kumbh-mela-how-a-superspreader-festival-seeded-covid-across-india>>.

in the ashrams situated in the forest. The Human Resource Development Minister gave a suggestion to this effect on Friday, the second day of the meeting of the Union Cabinet and top officials.¹⁹

Here the targets of the satire are the ministers, who are obliquely criticised for giving more importance to spiritual and religious education than to non-confessional education. This satirical short story, titled *Kaibinet kī baiṭhak meṃ śikṣā mantrī kā sujhāv, yūnīvarsitī kī jagah gurukul meṃ parh'ne chātr, gāy bhi pāleṅge* ("Culture Minister's Suggestion in Cabinet: Students to Study in Gurukul, They Will Also Look After Cows"), re-used some of the criticisms of the management of the university during the pandemic that had already been adopted in the previous days. Such criticism of the 'saffronisation' of the Indian public sphere during the coronavirus was echoed in other satirical fake news.

In other cases, however, the satirical fake news seems to have tended to legitimise some of the cultural views and symbolism supported by the Indian cultural 'mainstream' during the pandemic. An interesting example is a text published on May 22, 2020, in which the author satirically narrates the role played by the protests of workers in the spreading of the pandemic in India during this historical period.

Pappū: Well, tell me whether the workers running on the roads are patriots or traitors?

Gappū: What's the big deal! Some will be patriots and some will be traitors! It's that easy! Identify them by their clothes!

Pappū: My gosh! You are impossible! Leave it! Tell me: is this journey of workers from Urmar Tanda to Jhumri Tilaiya in the national interest or against it?

Gappū: Their journey is in their interest.

Pappū: And the nation's?

Gappū: You can answer. I don't like questions.

It is clear that this running around of workers spreads Covid 19. This is against the national interest, isn't it? Leave the workers alone. Tell

19 nāi dillī. viś'vavidyālaya khat'm hone ke bād sambhav hai ki ucc śikṣā ke lie ācāryom kā cayan kiyā jāe. ācārya vanom meṃ shit āśram meṃ rahenge. is āśay kā sujhāv kend'rīya mantrīmaṇḍal ālā afsarom kī baiṭhak ke dūs're din śukr'vār ko mānav saṃsādhan vikās mantrī ne diyā.

Cfr. the satirical news available at:

<<https://www.jansatta.com/humour/coronavirus-now-students-will-study-in-gurukul-instead-of-university-also-have-to-take-care-of-cows-says-education-minister/1422961/>>.

me, Gappū, what do you think about these politicians who are arranging trains and buses for them?²⁰

Leaving beside the political dimension of these texts, it is interesting to note that their author generally tends to re-use in his texts cultural views and stereotypes which were commonly used in the Indian public sphere and which, as previously noted, refers to many social categories. This re-use is always filtered by the creative dimension of satire and allows the author to introduce the readers of the columns to different ethical, socio-cultural and political questions. By moving in this direction, the satires sometimes de-construct those cultural assumptions; in other cases, like in the previous satire, they back some 'mainstream' narratives. In any case, unlike the proper fake news narratives, the last-quoted satirical fake news item has also an informative dimension in keeping the questions open to different answers and interpretations from the reading public.

6. Conclusions

Ajay Shukla's *asatya khab'reṃ* display their adherence to the category of the satirical news, a type of satire characterized by the humorous and grotesque emulation of proper news. Not unlike other texts which can be encapsulated in this class, they reveal distinct socio-cultural functions, especially in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic. The author often creatively re-adapts in his columns some of the cultural stereotypes and views that emerged in India during the pandemic, usually in order to either debunk some of them, or to enable, by virtue of a grotesque and humorous lens, a reflection on these topics. The columns also establish some counter-narratives concerning the management of the pandemic by the administration. From an aesthetical perspective, it is worth noting that these texts, despite their clear-cut adherence to contemporary Indian society and culture, are also inspired by a variety

20 Pappū: acchā, ye batāie ki saṛakoṃ par bhāg'te maz'dūr rāṣṭr'bhakt haiṃ yā rāṣṭr'drohi? Gappū: ismeṃ kyā! kuch rāṣṭr'bhakt hoṃge kuch rāṣṭr'drohi. it's izī. kap'rom se pah'cān lo. Pappū: ma gās!! yū ār impāsibal! choṛo. ye batāo ki maz'dūrom kī yah Uṛ'mar tāṇḍā se Jhum'rītilaiyā kī yatrā rāṣṭr'hit meṃ hai yā khilāf? Gappū: un'kī yatrā un'ke hit meṃ hai. Pappū: aur rāṣṭr ke? Gappū: tum batāo. mujh'ko savāl vaise bhī nāpasand hai. Pappū: sāf hai ki maz'dūrom kī is bhāg'daur se Koviḍ 19 phail'tā hai. Yah to rāṣṭr'hit ke khilaf huā na? calo, maz'dūrom ko choṛo. ye netā log jo in'ke tren aur bas kā int'zām kar rahe haiṃ, un'ke bare meṃ kyā vicār hai? bolo, Gappū bolo. Cfr. the satirical news available at:

<<https://www.jansatta.com/humour/coronavirus-discussion-between-pappu-and-gappu-on-travel-of-migrant-workers-during-covid-19/1412502/>>.

of motifs which are quite common in the earlier history of Hindi literary satire. An important element which connects these texts to other “mediatic” satirical texts of the past regards the use of spiritual, mystical and religious values. Shared by all these texts is the pivotal idea of using literary columns, often emulating other genres, to communicate ideological, socio-cultural and informative values during historical periods characterized by deep political instability.

References

- Ahmed, W. et al. 2020. “COVID-19 and the 5G Conspiracy Theory: Social Network Analysis of Twitter Data”. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*. 22, 5, Article e19458. DOI: 10.2196/19458
- Bhanot D. et al. 2021. “Stigma and Discrimination During COVID-19 Pandemic”. *Front Public Health*. 8, 577018. DOI: 10.3389/fpubh.2020.577018
- Boggero, Giovanni. 2020. “La satira come libertà ad ‘autonomia ridotta’ nello Stato costituzionale dei doveri.” *Nomos: le attualità del diritto*. 1, pp. 1–69.
Available at: <<https://www.nomos-leattualitaneldiritto.it/nomos/giovanni-boggero-la-satira-come-liberta-ad-autonomia-ridotta-nello-stato-costituzionale-dei-doveri/>>. Last access 01/01/2025.
- Cariguel, O. 2017. “Un volatile centenaire: ‘le Canard enchaîné.’” *Revue Des Deux Mondes*. pp. 186–188.
- Declercq, D. 2021. *Satire, Comedy and Mental Health: Coping with the Limits of Critique*. Bingley, Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Diehl, N. 2013. “Satire, Analogy, and Moral Philosophy”. *The Journal of Aesthetics and Art Criticism*. 71(4), pp. 311–321. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jaac.12030>
- Ellis-Petersen, H. Hassan, A. (2020): “Kumbh-Mela: How a Super-spreader Festival Seeded Covid Across India”. The Guardian.
Available at:
<<https://www.theguardian.com/world/2021/may/30/kumbh-mela-how-a-superspreader-festival-seeded-covid-across-india>>.
Last access 20/10/2024.
- Gallerani, G.M. 2022. *L'intervista immaginata: da genere mediatico a invenzione letteraria*. Firenze University Press: Firenze. DOI: 10.36253/978-88-5518-556-1
- Golbeck, J. et al. 2018. “Fake news vs satire: a dataset and analysis”. *Proceedings of the 10th ACM conference on web science*. Amsterdam:

- Netherlands: Association for Computing Machinery, 17–21. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3201064.3201100>
- Harder, Hans. 2012. "Towards a Concept of Colonial Satire in South Asian Literatures". *Indian Satire in the Period of First Modernity* (eds. Monika Hortsmann et. al.). Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, pp. 165–181.
- Hedrick, E. 2017. "A Modest Proposal in Context: Swift, Politeness, and A Proposal for giving Badges to the Beggars". *Studies in Philology*, 114, 4, 852–874.
- Horne, B. D., & Adali, S. 2017. "This just in: Fake news packs a lot in title, uses simpler, repetitive content in text body, more similar to satire than real news". *Eleventh international AAAI conference on web and social media*, pp. 759–766. DOI: 10.1609/icwsm.v11i1.14976.
- Jain, S. & Shivaprasad, M. 2022. "Anti-caste Memes as Cultural Archives of Resistance". *Culture Unbound*, 14, 2, pp. 153–178. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3384/cu.3956>
- Kamleśvar, Prasād S. 1966. *Nayī kahānī kī bhūmikā*. Nāī Dillī: Akṣar Prakāśan Limiṭeḍ.
- Low, J. F. et al. 2022. "Distinguishing between fake news and satire with transformers". *Expert Syst. Appl.* 187, 115824. DOI: 10.1016/j.eswa.2021.115824
- Mangravit, F. 2020. "'If You Cheat on Someone You Will Get Pleasure': The Oblique Reception of Kabīr's Teachings in Harishankar Parsāī's Hindi Satirical Short Stories". *Zeitschrift für Indologie und Südasiestudien*, 37, pp. 59–95.
- . 2023. Haṁso haṁsāo, Coronavirus ko dūr bhagāo: Hindi satire and humour as psychological and ideological resources during the COVID-19 crisis. *The COVID-19 Pandemic in Asia and Africa. Societal Implications, Narratives on Media, Political Issues. Volume I – culture, art, media* (eds. Milanetti, G. et al.). Roma: Sapienza Università Editrice, pp. 37–70. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.13133/9788893772990>.
- Martin, L. 2000. "Pourquoi lit-on 'Le Canard enchaîné'? Vingtième Siècle". *Revue d'histoire*, 68, pp. 43–53. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3406/xxs.2000.3934>
- Martin, L. 2003. "Le Canard enchaîné, un 'objet politique mal identifié.'" *Revue d'histoire Moderne et Contemporaine (1954-)*, 50, 2, pp. 73–91. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3917/rhmc.502.0073>
- Owens, J. 2019. "Post-authenticity and the Ironic Truths of Meme Culture". *Post Memes, Seizing the Memes of Production* (eds. Bown, A. et al.). Punctum Books.
- Palermo, M. 2016. "I falsi del Male, alle radici della parodia postmoderna?" *Linguaggio e comicità. Lingua, dialetti e mistilinguismo nell'in-*

- trattenimento comico tra vecchi e nuovi media* (eds. Covino, S. et al.), Bern: Peter Lang, pp. 197–218.
- Palermo, M. 2019. "Post-verità e parodia: dai giornali ai cartacei ai social media". *KWARTALNIK NEOFILOLOGICZNY*, LXVI, 2. DOI: 10.24425/kn.2019.128416
- Rogers, R.; Niederer, S. 2020. "The Politics of Social Media Manipulation." In: *The Politics of Social Media Manipulation* (eds. Rogers, R. et al.). Amsterdam University Press, pp. 19–70. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv1b0fvs5.3>
- Samantaray, R. 2024. "'Taj Mahal ki Tender': A Satirical Highlight at Bharat Ranga Mahotsava 2024". *Chitralkha*. Available at: <https://chitralkha.co.in/ramakanta-samantaray-on-taj-mahal-ki-tender-theatre/>. Last access 20/12/2024.
- Simpson, P. 2000. "Satirical Humour and Cultural Context: with a Note on the Curious Case of Father Todd Unctuous". *Contextualised Stylistics: In Honour of Peter Verdonk* (eds. Bex, A. et al.). Amsterdam: Rodopi, 243–266.
- Sood, A. 2020. "No Country for Political Satire: How Much Can Indian Comedy Really Push the Boundaries". *DeadAnt*. Available at: <https://deadant.co/no-country-for-political-satire/>. Last access 20/10/2024.
- Śukla, A. 2020. "Vyaṅgya: svarg ke geṭ se lauṭāe gae jumman, Citragupt ne kahā: abhī din pūre nahīm hue". *Jan'sattā*. Available at: <https://www.jansatta.com/humour/how-religious-discrimination-affecting-indias-culture-and-image-read-this-story/1435152/>. Last access 25/10/2024.
- Śukla, A. 2020. "Humour: mazdūr kī yatrā ke khilāf, savāl mujhe pasand nahīm". *Jan'sattā*. Available at: <https://www.jansatta.com/humour/coronavirus-discussion-between-pappu-and-gappu-on-travel-of-migrant-workers-during-covid-19/1412502/>. Last access 20/10/2024.
- Śukla, A. 2020. "Kaibineṭ kī baiṭhak meṃ śikṣā mantrī kā sujhāv, yūniversiṭī kī jagah gurukul meṃ paṛh'ne chātr, gāy bhi pālemge". *Jan'sattā*. Available at: <https://www.jansatta.com/humour/coronavirus-now-students-will-study-in-gurukul-instead-of-university-also-have-to-take-care-of-cows-says-education-minister/1422961/>. Last access 20/10/2024.
- Śukla, A. 2020. "Gaṅjā-bhāmg kī bhī dukāneṃ khuleṃ, vārnā dās hazār naṣebāz Kaśī Viśvanāth ke āge deṃge dharnā". *Jan'sattā*.

Available at: <<https://www.jansatta.com/humour/covid-19-ways-to-improve-the-economy-in-this-corona-crisis/1420840/>> Last access 25/10/2024.

Vanzi, A. 2023. "Quando Calvino scrisse sul <<Male>> (poi venne l'Immobilismo molisano). Incontro. Angelo Pasquini ricorda i classici falsi e la vera anticipazione di un capitolo dello scrittore sul <<Male>>". *Il Manifesto*.

Available at: <<https://ilmanifesto.it/quando-calvino-scrisse-sul-male-poi-venne-limmobilismo-molisano>>. Last access 25/10/2024.

Yu, H. 2024. "COVID-19, Satirical Activism, and Chinese Youth Culture: An Introduction". *Global Storytelling: Journal of Digital and Moving Images*, 3, 2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3998/gi.5303>

Fabio Mangravit